

Reconfigurable Photonic Convolutional Neural Network

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Abstract—This article, proposes a reconfigurable photonic quantum tensor core (PQTC), an array of reconfigurable photonic gates (RPG) arranged in a systematic way. The designed RPG provides the features namely broadband operation, low insertion loss and compact layout. The polarization encoding and intensity encoding is adopted as the quantum states to represents the image pixels. The reconfiguration of RPG is accomplished using electro-optic P-i-N carrier injection mechanism. As compared to silicon photonic block based on Mach-Zehnder interferometer (MZI), the proposed silicon RPG provide scalable operation based on mode coupling mechanism. The RPG is modeled using 2D finite element beam propagation method (FE-BPM) method. Finally, a compact numerical model (CNM) is developed and verified using MATLAB to check its suitability for deep learning applications.

Index Terms—reconfigurable photonic gate, quantum computing, mode coupling mechanism, photonic neural network.

I. Introduction

THE application specific photonic ICs perform dedicated functions, where the function can not be altered after manufacturing. Reconfigurable photonic ICs are capable of performing multiple functionality in the same photonic IC after manufacturing, which reduces the development time, and cost and leads to hardware flexibility. The reconfigurable photonic IC is implemented with different structures such as square, rectangular, triangular and hexagonal with array of either 2×2 MZI or 2×2 directional couplers. With the suitable configuration of each element, the required photonic applications can be mapped. The MZI based photonic array resulted more insertion loss and larger layout dimensions, which limits the dense integration of configurable Mach-Zehnder interferometer (MZI) [1]. Some of the most important issues in MZI are the phase-error, larger-foot print and power imbalance due to asymmetric nature of upper and lower arms. The phase-errors in MZI switch leads to an undesirable interference effects other than required constructive and destructive interferences. Due to this problem MZI switches are not suitable for ON-OFF switching applications. However, with the provision of two phase-shifters in the upper and lower arm the undesired interference effect will be compensated even

after the fabrication. In these, one phase-shifter is used for controlling the phase-error and the other is used to provide required phase shift.

For silicon based MZI switches, modulation and phase-shifting operation are realized using free carrier plasma dispersion effect by following any one of the mechanism namely, carrier injection (forward biased P-i-N junction), carrier depletion (reverse biased P-N junction), and carrier accumulation (MOS capacitor structure). In P-i-N configurations, the carrier injection in the intrinsic silicon waveguide changes the total carrier concentration of the waveguide core, which in turn changes the refractive index and absorption coefficient. Due to the change in refractive index, the propagation constant also be changed, this makes the light to slow-down. The carrier-injection produces insertion loss due to the free-carrier absorption. At the same time, addition of phase-shifter increases the insertion loss, the larger-foot print of the MZI structure is not suitable for large-scale integration of photonic components. A recent review of different types of photonic switches have been given in [2]. The intrinsic problems of the individual directional coupler such as cross talk due to the undesirable coupling and the attenuation makes approximately 100 % power transfer. So, with one of the port is terminated with highly doped silicon material [3], enables the directional coupler suitable for ON-OFF switching applications [4].

Artificial neural network (ANNs) are emerging due to its proven ability to solve complex real world problems. The features such as faster and power efficient operation of photonic circuit has made it suitable for ANNs. The inherent wavelength multiplexing capability make the photonic circuit to handle multiple light signals in parallel, which ensures faster operation. The photonic component which uses mode coupling mechanism [5, 6] occupies less foot print compared to the photonic component which uses the interferometric principles. Due to this reduced footprint, it consumes lesser power compared to digital electronic counterpart.

The high performance machine learning applications require an alternate approach of using photonic processing engine (PPE) compared to conventional graphics processing units (GPUs) [7]. In this work, we developed a PPE that performs the multiplications of matrices in

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parallel using a multiple wavelengths, shows an efficient approach for achieving high performance in deep learning applications. In our current approach, the feed-forward photonic network is adopted with the trained inference data suitable for unsupervised learning applications. For this we designed, a 1×1 reconfigurable photonic gate, which provides a degree of freedom in arbitrary intensity for the input signal to be processed. Using the RPG, we designed a photonic processing engine to perform the complex matrix multiplications required in ANNs. The degree of freedom in arbitrary power coupling and the phase shifts are realized using the P-i-N junction configuration [8]. The proposed photonic processing engine find applications in the field programmable photonic arrays [9], deep learning ANNs, microwave photonics, optical switching, waveguide meshes [10], digital photonics [11] and high speed data centers.

II. Reconfigurable silicon photonic gate

The electro-optic modulation in silicon photonics can be achieved by two means with the help of plasma dispersion effect commonly known as phase-shifters. One is using creating a P-i-N junction, where a carrier injection mechanism is involved and the second one is using PN junction, where carrier depletion principle is used. The refractive index of the silicon is controlled by means of varying the density of the charge carriers in the intrinsic silicon waveguide. The change in refractive index (Δn) by the change of carrier density at 1550 nm is described as follows [12]. However, the change in carrier density also leads to the change in absorption ($\Delta\alpha$) of the waveguide, which can be described as follows:

$$\Delta n = -5.4 \times 10^{-22} \Delta N^{1.011} - 1.53 \times 10^{-18} \Delta P^{0.838} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta\alpha = 8.88 \times 10^{-21} \Delta N^{1.167} + 5.84 \times 10^{-20} \Delta P^{1.109} \quad (2)$$

where ΔN and ΔP are the carrier densities of electrons and holes [cm^3] respectively.

A new type of photonic component is developed using mode coupling mechanism with a phase shifter to provide the desired attenuation and the required phase shift in the incoming light.

$$\begin{bmatrix} o1 \\ o2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{1-\kappa} & i\sqrt{\kappa} \\ i\sqrt{\kappa}e^{i\Delta\phi} & \sqrt{1-\kappa}e^{i\Delta\phi} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i1 \\ i2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The Fig.1 shows the schematic representation of the proposed 1×1 RPG, which includes a directional coupler and a phase-shifter. The power coupling coefficient in the directional coupler controls the amount of light intensity to be given as an output. The phase shifter have a control over the output light which serves two purposes. One is to introduce the required phase shift for the output light and the other one is the provide required rotation for the linear unitary operations. This 1×1 RPG has an advantage of behaving like an arbitrary reconfigurable attenuator.

The basic 1×1 reconfigurable photonic gate (RPG) is designed using FE-BPM and an quasi-rigorous compact numerical model (CNM) is developed using MATLAB to

utilize the RPG in the larger photonic circuits. The design of RPG using different methods ensures the accuracy of the RPG, which helps to analysis the large scale photonic circuits in an efficient way. We adopted the silicon on insulator (SoI) platform to design the RPG and for the analysis of large scale photonic circuit. In the SoI platform, a silicon device layer is bonded to a SiO_2 layer deposited on the silicon substrate. The dimensions of the silicon device layer is 500×220 nm with slab height of 90 nm. The upper and lower cladding of SiO_2 of thickness of $2 \mu m$ size is considered. the transverse-electric (TE) polarization is employed in the simulation [13, 14].

The voltage-power coupling coefficient relation is shown in Fig.2, the relationship is less stable beyond 1.1 V, since the increase of voltage leads to abrupt change in power coupling factor. Hence, it is recommended to use the voltage range from 0 to 1.15 V to get various power coupling values. A compact numerical model (CNM) is

Fig. 1. The schematic representation of 1×1 reconfigurable photonic gate acts as the unit cell for photonic processing.

Fig. 2. The relationship between the applied driving voltage and the power coupling coefficient.

developed based on the s-parameters obtained using the Lumerical MODE and verified using INTERCONNECT [15, 16]. Here the designed 1×1 RPG, the input and output is related based on the intensity required and controlled by the power coupling coefficient. The OFF-state is achieved by setting the power coupling coefficient ($\kappa \approx 0$). The CNM is coded with MATLAB and an array of 4×4 RPG is developed and verified as follows.

III. 5×5 photonic quantum tensor core

The basic relationship between the inputs and the associated weight vectors are relate by the equations from (3) to (9). The feed-forward network with 4×4 convolutional kernel is developed using the proposed 1×1 RPG is shown in Fig.3). Here the four inputs x_1 , x_2 , x_3 , and x_4 represents four unique intensity values. The different levels of intensity are obtained using the respective power coupling factor associated with each RPG. The convolutional kernel used in the proposed work

Fig. 3. The 4x4 photonic processing engine, includes an array of 1×1 RPGs.

is given in equation (3), which represents the attenuation factor.

$$W_{4 \times 4} = \begin{bmatrix} w_{11} & w_{12} & w_{13} & w_{14} \\ w_{21} & w_{22} & w_{23} & w_{24} \\ w_{31} & w_{32} & w_{33} & w_{34} \\ w_{41} & w_{42} & w_{43} & w_{44} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$Y = X^T \cdot W_{4 \times 4} \quad (5)$$

$$Y = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} w_{11} & w_{12} & w_{13} & w_{14} \\ w_{21} & w_{22} & w_{23} & w_{24} \\ w_{31} & w_{32} & w_{33} & w_{34} \\ w_{41} & w_{42} & w_{43} & w_{44} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$y_1 = x_1 w_{11} + x_2 w_{21} + x_3 w_{31} + x_4 w_{41} \quad (7)$$

$$y_2 = x_1 w_{12} + x_2 w_{22} + x_3 w_{32} + x_4 w_{42} \quad (8)$$

$$y_3 = x_1 w_{13} + x_2 w_{23} + x_3 w_{33} + x_4 w_{43} \quad (9)$$

$$y_4 = x_1 w_{14} + x_2 w_{24} + x_3 w_{34} + x_4 w_{44} \quad (10)$$

From the equation 7, the node y_1 represents the linear combinations of inputs x_1 , x_2 , x_3 , and x_4 with its associated weight factors. Each input represents the intensity levels and hence the node y_1 have the consolidated intensity values of all the inputs and the linear proportions are determined by its respective weight vectors. The phase shifter inside the 1×1 RPG is useful to represent the negative value of the weight vector and serves to

introduce the required rotation operation in the linear unitary applications [17].

Fig. 4. The output intensity obtained from the 1×1 RPG when $\kappa=1$ with $V_k=1.1$ V

Fig. 5. The output intensity from the 1×1 RPG when $\kappa=0$ with $V_k=0$ V

Fig. 6. The output intensity from the 1×1 RPG when $\kappa=0.5$ with $V_k=0.91$ V.

IV. Results and Discussion

The voltage requirement to achieve the desired intensity level is illustrated in the Fig.2. The broad range of coupling coefficients are obtained using different voltage levels.

Fig. 7. The linear combinations of input intensities x_1 , x_2 , x_3 , and x_4 with its weight vectors at node y_1 , y_2 , y_3 , and y_4 for an arbitrary weight vectors.

But, before configuring the weight obtained from the trained feed-forward network, the desired voltage levels are mapped to create the required intensity levels. If multiple wavelengths are considered to represent each input, the node y_1 may have all the inputs scaled by the corresponding weight values and have collectively all the wavelengths and represents an intensity value that have multiple wavelengths. This may require additional wavelength selective filters to separate the wavelengths from the processing node before passing to the next stage. The sample intensity levels are shown in Figs.4, Figs.5, and Figs.6 for the voltage of $V=1.1$, 0, and 0.91 respectively. For an arbitrary value of inputs and weight vectors, the results are shown in Fig.7.

V. Conclusion

In this work, we designed a compact 1×1 reconfigurable photonic gate (RPG) using silicon platform with with P-i-N carrier injection mechanism for power coupling and phase shift. The proposed photonic processing engine (PPE) acts as the basic block for larger artificial neural network applications. The designed PPE, provides faster operation and reduced power consumption compared to the electronic counterpart. Due to the reduced foot-print, the proposed silicon PPE is suitable for large-scaled reconfigurable photonic integrated circuit applications.

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